

Overview of Educational Services in Nigerian Public Universities for Sustainable Development

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Abstract

The paper examines Assessment of educational services in Nigerian Public Universities for sustainable national development. In attempt to address this, issues such as, Concept of educational services, Challenges of educational services, concept of sustainable national development, sustainable development, goals of sustainable development, University Education and Sustainable National Development: The Relationship, Policy implications, challenges of university education in Nigeria has been discussed. The paper therefore concluded that, managing educational services in Nigerian universities for sustainable development requires a multi-faceted approach that encompasses effective leadership, innovative strategies, quality management, ICT integration, human resource management, and sound financial practices. By implementing these strategies, Nigerian universities can enhance the quality of education, foster research and innovation, and contribute significantly to the country's sustainable development goals. The Paper recommended that, Government at all levels should provide adequate funds for the educational institutions particularly universities that are the apex of education, and Finally, Infrastructural facilities in universities in Nigeria should be provided.

Keywords: Educational Services, Public Universities, Sustainable Development

Introduction

University Education is an important key of achieving a sustainable national development in Nigeria. For a state or society to achieve a sustainable national development, the quality of its education should be improved by providing students with adequate materials, facilities, equipment and other relevant educational services that will aid teaching and learning process. University Education is a vital instrument for national and sustainable development and it involves the acquisition of fundamental knowledge and essential development skills needed for technological breakthrough and socio-political development which accelerates economic growth (Josephine & Doris 2019). Provision of education/students' services help in the attainment of goals and objectives of university education in Nigeria. These services include among others health services, guidance and counseling services, hostel accommodation services, water supply services, security services, transport services, library services, games and sports services, food services, social services, religious services etc.

According to the National Policy on Education (2018) University Education shall make contribution to national development by:

1. Intensifying and diversifying its programmes for the development of high-level manpower within the context of the needs of the nation;
2. making professional course contents reflect our national requirements;
3. making all students part of a general programme or all-round improvement in university education to offer general study contents such as history of ideas, philosophy of knowledge, nationalism and Information Technology (IT); and
4. vi Making entrepreneurial skills acquisition a requirement for Nigerian universities.

Education services are an integral component of the education system especially universities that are charged with the responsibility of providing highly skilled man power for the attainment of educational goals at all levels of the educational system from pre-primary to higher education Institutions. School goal achievement factors do not only stop in teaching and learning activities, but includes other activities and provision of facilities within the school system. This is outlined to address the challenges of school services towards getting more alternatives of providing these services using the least and available resources in an environmentally friendly manner.

Concept of Education Services at the University Level

Jumare (2016) defines educational services as the university function in respect of the provision of materials that aid teaching and learning within and outside the university environment. Students' services are essential because it serves as lubricant in achieving the set institution goals and objectives. Educational services should be seen as intervening variables in the achievement of university goals of teaching and learning in these institutions of higher learning.

Types of Educational Services at University Level

Students are the central focus of school administration, therefore whatever the school does he must put the students into consideration. Universities are set up not for lecturers or teachers, not university administrators not for parents but the students. Based on this, the services which the university is expected to render to then students for the development of their physical, material and emotional well-being include

1. **Discipline and control of students:** The concept of discipline is capable of various interpretations. With special reference to the university system however, discipline is often referred to as when students are taught to respect the institution authorities to observe the university rules and regulations and to maintain an established standard of behavior. Therefore, students discipline means students are provided with an opportunity to exercise self-control to institutions problems and to learn to promote the welfare of the institution.
2. **Students' health services:** Health services connotes provision and maintenance of health facilities in the university system. Health facilities include drugs, medical equipment, nurses, the clinic and storage facilities.
3. **Guidance and counseling:** Guidance and Counseling services guide students on academic, social and development matters on campus for better academic performance. Good services in guidance reduce mass failure in examination and help reduce time wastage among students especially in subject selection and career choice.
4. **Students' Recreational facilities:** Sport or Recreational services in the university system are facilities or equipment and persons provided to assist students exercise their body at a stipulated time. Games facilities such as balls, fields, coaches, time and other facilities are made available to students. Recreational facilities should be in an open place or in-door. In any case there is the need for the provision of enough facilities with an effective management.
5. **Hostel accommodation services:** Hostel accommodation services to refer to provision of place and facilities required by students to live and aid learning. The facilities could include among others power supply, water supply, toilet facility, and others. Hostel services give students rest for better energy regain for learning.
6. **Students' academic adviser services:** Student's adviser is a lecturer assign to students for consultations. Each student is attached to a lecturer., however, teachers do have several students under their care. These lecturers are expected to understand student's strengths and weaknesses for advice. This interaction assist involving students in both academic and social challenges.
7. **School community services:** School community services imply duties and benefits the community gives to the university and the university gives to the community. The mutual relationship between the university and the community assists the university achieve goals and in the end the university graduates to assist or solve societal problems or challenges at work force. Thus, with this it has become imperative to encourage this kind of services among the education stakeholders. Others are. Transportation services, Library services, Food services, social services, religious services, Water supply services, Electricity services, social services and Commercial services.

Importance of Students' Services in the University System

Students' services are essential in the administration of university for the attainment of the set goals and objectives for the well-being of both staff and students. Jumare (2016) outline the following as the general importance of students' services include; Protect life and property of both staff and students; Guides students on rules and regulations of the university; Protect and prevent students from direses; Increase academic performance among students; Increase discipline behaviour

among students; Inculcate the culture of reading in students; Eases students transport in and outside the university; Eases students access to books, foods and other needs; Protects and promotes students' rights

Challenges of school services at university level

Educational services face a lot of challenges in the university system in Nigeria. Some of these are as follows: Inadequate forecasting mechanism in universities; Low budget allocation to education and to universities in particular; Lack of maintenance culture among university administrators; Inadequate commitment from university administrators and other staff in the university; High cost of facility management; Inadequate security to provide facilities required; Lack of university autonomy; High enrolment explosion in the universities especially public universities; strategies for providing the service effectively and efficiently

Concept of Sustainable National Development

Adekeye (2013) views Sustainable development as an ethical framework for using the nation's resources efficiently, creating effective infrastructures and relationships, protecting and enhancing the quality of lives, and creating new business channels to strengthen the economy. Sustainable development is also referred to as the state of maintaining and ensuring constant development of the people, or the socioeconomic, political, and cultural survival of a nation from one generation to the other. Everything about sustainable development is geared towards the future generation. It asks this question: how can we use the natural resources at our disposal bearing in mind our children, grandchildren, great grandchildren, just to mention a few? We need to meet our needs without compromising the need of the future generation. This is the reason education should aim to develop particular attitudes and values such as solidarity, social justice and environment awareness in the education institutions. It also needs to equip the student with adequate knowledge and skills so as to empower him/her to transform the society. (Osuji 2015)

Therefore, the concept of sustainable national Development remains the modern parameter of measuring development. (Abubakar 2013). Munasinghe (2011) opines that sustainable national Development is a process of improving the range of opportunities that will enable individual humans and communities to achieve their aspirations and full potential over a sustained period of time while maintaining the resilience of economic, social and environmental systems. Age (2013), identified some objectives which sustainable national development is expected to realize: increase capital income and employment, promoting human welfare satisfying basic needs; protecting the environment. Considering the path of future generation, achieving equity between rich and poor and participation on a broad basis in development and decision making is important.

The term "sustainable development" was initially coined in 1972 during the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment and later gained prominence by way of a report to the United Nations by the "World Commission on Environment and Development" which was chairperson by the Prime Minister of Norway "Gro Harlem Brundtland" (Waas, Huge, Verbruggen & Wright, 2011). Sustainable development entails that resources that are renewable should be employed in every possible situation and resources that are non-renewable should be used rarely in order to ensure their viability for the future generations to come (Patil, 2014). Sustainable development entails the designing of a social and economic system that ensures that standards of education continue to improve, the rise in the real income is maintained, the economic growth of the nation continues to improve as well as other aspect of life continues to increase (Kyro, 2015).

This cannot occur if the right type of education is not given to individuals. Sustainable development can be viewed in three dimensions namely; Economic, environmental and social (United Nations, 2005).

Goals of Sustainable Development

The goals of sustainable development include:

1. End of poverty in all its forms across boards.
2. Establish infrastructures while promoting inclusive and sustainable commercialization while fostering innovations.
3. Ensure healthy lives and promotion of well-being for all.
4. Guaranty equal and inclusive education while promoting long-lasting learning opportunities for all.
5. Ensuring gender equity and empowerment of females.
6. Guarantee available and sustainable management of water and sanitation for everyone
7. Available employment for everyone across boards.
8. Mitigate the inequality within and among nations.
9. Ensure that cities and settlement are safety conscious, inclusive and sustainable.

10. Guarantee sustainable consumption and production patterns.
11. Embark on actions that tackle climate changes its implications.
12. Preserve and sustainable employ oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development.
13. Provision of access to justice while building accountable and inclusive institutions at all level of governance.

From these goals mentioned above it can be deduced that the objective sustainable is focused on reconciling the issues of economic development that is necessary for higher standard of living with that of enhancing with the challenges being faced in the Nigerian space today. Hence, entrepreneurship can aid in fostering sustainable development.

University Education and Sustainable National Development

Having stated above, the various definitions of education and sustainable national development, it is imperative to examine the relationship between the two concepts. In all nations, Nigeria inclusive, education remains the instrument for effective national development. Development is championed through education, which is often assumed to have significant influence. Education entails the enlightenment of people in their ways of pursuit in life. Development is associated with a positive change in the condition of either individual groups, communities or even a country as a whole (Umoh, 2010). Education and sustainable national development are interwoven, intertwined, and interconnected. While on the one hand, development is geared towards producing or creating something new or more advanced for the society and its members. On the other hand, education is a tool which can enhance the desired sustainable development. Umoh, 2010 therefore, refers education and sustainable development as two sides of the same coin. The fact that education and sustainable development shows glaring connectivity probably explained why scholars emphasized the need for education for the purpose of achieving the desired sustainable development.

Education provides consciousness, awareness and enlightenment to individuals in order to properly pursue their aspirations and yearnings. It is only educated population that can command skills necessary for sustainable economic growth and a better quality of life. Sustainable national development may therefore be seen as the target goal since it is meant for the society and its members; education however remains the instrument for achieving and attaining the target goal. From the above, education seems to directly determine whether sustainable national development is going to be achieved or not and therefore, the need for a well-structured educational system that will enhance the achievement of the aforementioned development. Osuji, (2015) stated “To be candid, this is what our society needs today for sustainable development”. We need graduates who are grounded in knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values and who are conscious of our natural environment; also, are able to transfer their wealth of knowledge for the sustained good of the society. In support of this, Pavlova (2013) affirms that sustainability is a value that is concerned with dealing with the natural environment and resources in such a way that we do not deprive future generations of the opportunities that we ourselves enjoy.

Policy Implications at University Level

According to Oguzor, (2011), University Education entails a recognition of the interdependence of people, the acquisition and cultivation of such virtues as caring for our fellow men, honesty, integrity, faithfulness, sympathy, thoughtfulness, trust and a healthy attitude towards work to mention only but a few. In its second National Development Plan, 1970-1974, Nigeria articulated a set of five national objectives. These means to build up: A free and democratic society; A just and egalitarian society; A united, strong and self-reliant nation; A great and dynamic economy; and A land of bright and full opportunity for all citizens.

In order to realize these objectives, universities were made to aim at: The acquisition, development and inculcation of paper value –orientation for the survival of the individual and society; The development of the intellectual capacities of individuals to understand and appreciate their environments; The acquisition of both physical and intellectual skills which will enable individuals to develop into useful members of the community; The acquisition of an objective view of the local and external environments.

Universities are the apex of academic learning. The teaching and research functions should have important roles to play in national development. That apart, universities had been known in the Western world to be one of the best means for developing national consciousness. Clearly, the Nigerian universities have not lived up to either the traditional objectives or the aims as set out in the National Policy on Education. They have not been particularly effective in directing the nation to the path of truth and equity. If this were different then indiscipline, corruption, disorder, and unpatriotic should no longer be the bane of the Nigerian society particularly among leaders. Perhaps what universities in Nigeria seem to have succeeded in doing is the development of intellectual capacities of the individual but unfortunately not to understand and appreciate the

environments rather, to exploit, cheat, and manipulate the environment for selfish purpose. The system has failed not only as a mechanism for westernization but also as an instrument for the identification, modification and codification of Nigerian cultural values. Consequently, universities have been a disastrous clash of cultures. The products are neither Western nor Nigerian. Perhaps the western values have really been understanding and appreciated while the local values are misunderstood, denigrated and sometimes discarded.

The 1962 UNESCO Tananarive Conference on the Development of Higher Education in Africa remarked the issues of reliance and identity as important factor in ensuring sustainable development through universities. The preamble of the Association of African Universities which followed the conference reads as follows. Conscious of the role of African Universities to maintain an adherence and loyalty to world academic standards, and to evolve over the years a pattern of higher education in service of Africa and its people, yet promoting a bond of kinship to the large human society". The significant points in the preamble include: The acceptance of the existence of a world standard; and the necessity to evolve a pattern suited to the need of Africa without disregarding the assumed world standards.

These are the challenges of universities in Nigeria as well. While it is, however, debatable whether there is indeed "universalisticness" in the world standard of universities, we may wish to take refuge in Sir Eric Ashby's remark that the African university should refurnish in the house of Western tradition and adapt their degree programme to fit the needs of the African society. But it must be noted that African universities cannot be engines of national development if their frame of reference is confined to local political predilections and ideologies as in the case of Tanzania particularly at the University of Dar-es-Salaam. Nigeria universities should enhance sustainable development by intensifying and diversifying their programmes within the context of the needs of culture, society and economy without prejudice to intellectual training in basic sciences and liberal arts. There needs to be effective machinery for the identification of the manpower needs. The universities will enhance national development when the quality of their graduates is improved through consultations between them, the employers of labour and the government. This must be followed with proper funding and links with the industrial sector to facilitate research. During the 21st century, it is increasingly evident that the societies which will survive are those that recognize that knowledge and ideas are critical to development. Indeed, the keys to the future are embodied in ideas, in research, in knowledge which can be modified and reorganized to improve the quality of life of the citizens as demonstrated in higher incomes, higher standards of education, better health and adequate nutrition. This is a challenge to universities. In addition, as the enabling environment and the rules of the game for industrialization is dramatically changing, the pivot of development are but information technology, aerospace, electronics, materials science, chemical and pharmaceuticals and the biological develop through biotechnology. The science bases for sustainable development will be provide by biotechnology, communication technology and computers. The players in this emerging industrial world of the 21st century will be those countries that have invested in the necessary skills through research at the frontiers of Physics, Chemistry, and Biology and of Engineering through the instrumentality of qualitative education particularly post-graduate studies. In view of this, Nigeria should choose between encouraging the mad rush for university paper qualifications otherwise known as degrees and the proliferation of the institutions to award such degrees or make emphasis on the heart of the matter: "relevance, usefulness and identity to be part of the 21st century crusade for sustainable development in consonance with the new world order of globalization, differentiation and interdependence which is propelling the east Asian Miracle.

Challenges of University Education in Nigeria

The fact is education constitutes the major instrument for sustainable human development and fulcrum around which every other activity revolves (Tahir, 2016) Nation which have recorded tremendous feats in the world heavily relied on the instrumentality of education. However, in Nigeria there seems to be a daily decline of educational standards. Although according to the former president Olusegun Obasanjo in his Presidential Speech on April,24, 2000 in Dakar Senegal, he attributed the educational falling standard to bad governance. In his speech; he stated that: Nigerian educational system as it stands is a living proof of the damages that bad governance can do to our society and social structure. Human beings are the architects and engineers of progressive change and development and they constitute the most important resource we can have internally. Tahir (2016), identified a number of daunting challenges which Nigerian education is confronted with. They are as follows: Gender equity in education; Dearth of teachers; Overcrowded classrooms; Inadequate infrastructures; Funding of education.

Conclusion

Managing educational services in Nigerian universities for sustainable development requires a multi-faceted approach that encompasses effective leadership, innovative strategies, quality management, ICT integration, human resource management, and sound financial practices. By implementing these strategies, Nigerian universities can enhance the quality of education, foster research and innovation, and contribute significantly to the country's sustainable development goals.

Recommendations

1. Government at all levels should provide adequate funds for the educational institutions particularly universities that are the apex of education
2. Lecture halls/theatres should be provided to cater for the enrolment explosion in the educational institutions in the country
3. Adequate instructional materials should be provided
4. Infrastructural facilities in universities in Nigeria should be provided

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